

Influence of Ca, Mn substitution on thermoelectric properties of SrTiO₃

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Abstract

Thermoelectric properties have been investigated for Sr_{0.5}Ca_{0.5}Ti_{1-x}Mn_xO₃ ($x = 0.25, 0.5, 0.75$) and Sr_{0.75}Ca_{0.25}Ti_{0.75}Mn_{0.25}O₃ polycrystalline samples synthesized by solid-state reaction method. Thermal conductivity, electrical resistivity, seebeck coefficient, power factor and figure of merit (ZT) of as prepared samples were studied. The substitution of Ca²⁺ in Sr²⁺ site or/and mixed valence Mn in Ti²⁺ site creates appreciable enhancement in the thermoelectric properties and shows increase in the figure of merit from 0.5 to 0.69 at room temperature. The enrichment of ZT around room temperature originates due to low electrical resistivity, low thermal conductivity and high seebeck coefficient of the investigated systems.

Keywords: Thermoelectric, Figure of merit, Power factor, seebeck, electrical resistivity and thermal conductivity, SrTiO₃ etc.,

References:

1. J.G. Bednoiz, K.A. Muller, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **52**, 2289(1984).
2. F. Gervais, B. Cales, P. Odier, *Mater. Res. Bull.* **22**, 1629(1987)
3. T. Feng, *Phys.Rev.* **86**, 627 (1982)
4. J.F. Schooley, W.R. Hosler, M.L. Cohen, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **12**, 474 (1964).
5. M.L. Cohen, *Phys. Rev.* **134**, A511 (1964).